

Impact of Credit Risk on Banks Profitability in Pakistan: Study of Conventional Banks

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Abstract

Credit risk (CR) management has become a crucial factor for banks in order to stay competitive and maximize profitability. Some of the most severe financial crises that the world has faced have been due to CR's ineffective management. According to the statistics for the Banking System in Pakistan (SBP, 2018), the CR for banking is on the rise, which poses a severe threat to the banks' financial health in Pakistan. This study's main objective is to determine how the CR of the commercial banks operating in Pakistan can influence their profitability. For this purpose, the study used a secondary research method and collected data from the official websites of 22 commercial banks. In addition, a sample size of 10 banks has been selected to ensure accuracy. Based on the market capitalization, ten banks with the most excellent market capitalization among all the commercial banks were selected. Risk management factors considered were the Non-performing Loan Ratio (NLP) and Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), while Return on Equity (ROE) and Return on Assets (ROA) were selected as the indicators of the banks' profitability. The study found that NLP and CAR directly affect and assess the profitability of Pakistan's major commercial banks.

Key words: Commercial banks, credit risk, panel data regression performance, profitability.

INTRODUCTION

Credit risk (CR) is like a certainty of loss or risk of default on a debt that may arise from a borrower failing to make required payments. One of the most critical risk factors for commercial banks to consider is CR. Effectively managing the CR for any particular commercial bank is extremely important to survive. It is also important to understand that some of the most significant financial crises that the world has faced have been due to the ineffective management of the CR. The mortgage crises that led to the financial crises of the entire world was also caused when financial institutions in United States became reckless in giving and recovering the credit. (Garr, 2013). The financial institutions need to understand the major reasons and factors behind the credit issues. In most of the cases it is the lack of coherence in credit policies that lead to the greatest problem in terms of CR management. Even if the policies exist, there is lack of due diligence from the side of operational area in implementing the policies to their core. Furthermore, when greater issues exist in terms of portfolio management, this also leads to an enhancement of the CR for any commercial organization specially that of a bank. Risk management could effectively be called the basis of core banking transaction and provides a guarantee to bank that its operations would be running without any hassle. Furthermore, the bank could be relieved that no major blow will be witnessed in its profitability. In true essence, CR management may not be the only type of risk that a bank may have to manage but there are other different types of risks as well, such as liquidity risk, operational risk, market risk (Abbas et al ,2014). However, what makes CR a special feature for Banks's risk management policy is the core nature of the banking operation. In this particular industry, the business survives on the fact as how effectively the credit provided and advances allowed to the clients are recovered. The greater would be the recovery, more feasible would be the business model of such organization. On the contrary if business lacks in this particular area of risk management they may witness a deterioration in their liquidity, profitability and ultimately their existence may be threatened. For this reason, unlike other business organizations, commercial banks have to be more concerned for CR management (Abbas et al 2014).

REVIEW OF PREVIOUS STUDIES

Hamza (2017) evaluated the effect of CR management on performance of banks in Pakistan. Technique used

for this evaluation was multiple regression analysis and analyzed the results by means of SPSS programming. The research describes that CR management have negative impact on the performance of banks. Alshatti (2015) reveals the effect of CR on the financial performance of Jordanian commercial banks. Factors utilized were leverage ratio, gross loans, Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), Return on Assets (ROA), and Return on Equity (ROE). This research suggests that these factors affect the profitability of commercial banks. Abbas et al. (2014) point out the effect of CR exposure on the banking sector's performance in Pakistan. Using the method of fixed-effect regression, the authors have analyzed the impact of non-performing loans, loan loss provisions, ROA, and ROE on the CR. The results uncover that the aggregate loan to aggregate ratio escalates the profitability of the bank. Abiola & Olasui (2014) examined the impact of CR management on the banks' performance in Nigeria. Samples taken from seven commercial banks, and the data utilized were from the year 2005-2011. The dependent factors employed were ROA and ROE, and independent factors were Non-performing loan (NLPR) and Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR). The result or consequences of research uncovers that CR management substantially affects Nigerian banks' productivity. Thus, Nigerian banks must focus on their CR management for effective performance. Li and Zou (2014) investigated that the European commercial banks concentrated more on the association between two factors. One is the CR Management routine regarding banks and their impacts on Banks' profitability. ROE and ROA were considered the profitability indicators, whereas CAR and NLPR were an estimated CR factor. They utilized the multivariate regression model and found an insignificant positive connection between CAR with ROE and ROA while noted the negative relationship between NLPR with ROE and ROA.

Adeusi et al. (2013) examined the effect of risk management on Nigerian banks' financial performance. Secondary data was utilized from the year 2006-2009. Samples were taken from 10 commercial banks, and the technique used was panel data estimation. Moreover, dependent factors utilized for estimating banks' productivities were ROA and ROE. In contrast, the independent factors employed were liquidity, credit, and capital risks, which incorporated non-performing and suspicious loans. An inverse relationship was indicated between ROE and the non-performing loans. Garr (2013) conducted the research to assess the variables that influence Ghana's commercial banking sector's CR. Secondary data was taken from the Bank of Ghana and Ghana Statistical Services using descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, and regression analysis. Research outcomes uncover that management ineffectiveness and gross domestic product per capita (GDPPC) positively correlated with CR. In contrast, money financial sector progress and government borrowings were contrarily related to CR. Akhter et al. (2011), in their research, analyzed the factors influencing the profitability of conventional banks in Pakistan. Data utilized was taken from the years 2006-2009. Techniques used for estimation were descriptive statistics and regression analysis. The factors utilized were gearing ratio, NLPR, ROA, and ROE. Research outcomes indicate that both elements have a substantial impact on the profitability of banks.

RESEARCH PROBLEM AND OBJECTIVE

According to the Statistics for the Banking System in Pakistan (SBP, 2018), the CR for banking is on the rise, which poses a severe threat to the banks' financial health in Pakistan. The main objective of this research study is to determine the impact of CR on bank profitability. The CR impact on the banks' profitability is analyzed considering three critical factors; Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), Non-performing Loan's Ration (NLPR), Net Loan to Total Assets (NLTA), and the combined impact of CR. Hence, the main objectives of this research study are listed as:

1. To determine the CAR's impact on the banks' profitability
2. To determine the NLPR's impact on the banks' profitability
3. To determine the NLTA's size impact on the banks' profitability
4. To evaluate the combined impact of CR on profitability

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

The following section presents the details of the research process and techniques used to conduct the study. It

described the research process to collect, assemble and evaluate the collected data. Moreover, it represented the tools used to collect the required data and highlight the whole process of data collection and analysis.

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
ROE	-2.1783	1.18131	100
NPLR	-2.1767	.75321	100
CAR	-1.9194	.30036	100
ROA	-3.5589	1.36616	100
NLTA	13.8523	2.09987	100

The above-presented table shows the average values of the variables. The standard deviation (SD) quantifies the variability. The SD is used to calculate the variance and it is one of the most important and prominent tool of statistics to measure the spread. In the example above, the SD calculated for ROE is indicating that it is 1.18% away from the data mean. Above table shows the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study from the period 2009 to 2018.

Correlations						
Control Variables		ROE	NPLR	CAR	ROA	NLTA
ROE	Correlation	1.000	-.157	.199	-.276	.336
	Significance (2-tailed)	.	.119	.047	.005	.001
	Df	0	98	98	98	98
NPLR	Correlation	-.157	1.000	.068	.505	.049
	Significance (2-tailed)	.119	.	.501	.000	.632
	Df	98	0	98	98	98
CAR	Correlation	.199	.068	1.000	.002	.364
	Significance (2-tailed)	.047	.501	.	.986	.000
	Df	98	98	0	98	98
ROA	Correlation	-.276	.505	.002	1.000	.365
	Significance (2-tailed)	.005	.000	.986	.	.000
	Df	98	98	98	0	98
NLTA	Correlation	.336	.049	.364	.365	1.000
	Significance (2-tailed)	.001	.632	.000	.000	.
	Df	98	98	98	98	0
ROE	Correlation	1.000	-.184	.087	-.454	
	Significance (2-tailed)	.	.068	.392	.000	
	Df	0	97	97	97	
NPLR	Correlation	-.184	1.000	.054	.524	
	Significance (2-tailed)	.068	.	.594	.000	
	Df	97	0	97	97	
CAR	Correlation	.087	.054	1.000	-.151	
	Significance (2-tailed)	.392	.594	.	.135	
	Df	97	97	0	97	
ROA	Correlation	-.454	.524	-.151	1.000	
	Significance (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.135	.	
	Df	97	97	97	0	

a. Cells contain zero-order (Pearson) correlations.

The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (also known as Pearson's correlation) indicates the strength and orientation of interaction between two variables calculated on an interval scale. Pearson's correlation is used to determine whether or not the variables have a relationship. The results show that the correlation coefficient of NPLR with return equity is negative (-.157) with a p-value of 0.119. CAR has a correlation coefficient of 19.9 percent with ROE and a p-value of 0.04, which indicates a statistically significant relationship between CAR and Return on Equity. NLTA has a correlation coefficient of 33.6 percent with Return on Equity with a p-value of 0.001, indicating a statistically significant relationship between NLTA and Return on Equity.

Moreover, NPLR has a correlation coefficient of 52.4 percent with ROA and a p-value of 0.00, indicating a statistically significant relationship between NPLR and ROA. CAR has a negative correlation coefficient (-.151) with ROA at a p-value of 0.135, showing a negative relationship between CAR and ROA. NLTA has a correlation coefficient of 36.5 with ROA at a p-value of 0.00, which indicates a statistically significant relationship between NLTA and ROA. However, after putting NLTA as a control variable, it has been found that NPLR has a correlation coefficient of -0.184 with ROE at a p-value of 0.068, indicating a statistically negative relationship between NPLR and ROE. CAR has a correlation coefficient of 8.7 percent with Return on Equity at a p-value of 0.392, which shows a statistically positive relationship between CAR and ROE. The NPLR value after putting NLTA is a correlation coefficient of 52.4 percent with ROA at a p-value of 0.00, which indicates a statistically positive relationship between NPLR and ROA. Furthermore, CAR has a correlation coefficient of -0.151 with ROA at a p-value of 0.135, which shows a negative relationship between CAR and ROA.

Hence, based on the correlation matrix, it has been found that NPLR has a negative relationship with ROE in both situations, with and without a control variable (NLTA). In contrast, NPLR has a positive relationship with ROA in both cases. Moreover, CAR has a positive relationship with ROE in both cases and a negative relationship with ROA.

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	-1.564	.364		-4.296	.000
	NLNPLR	.917	.158	.505	5.798	.000
2	(Constant)	-1.841	.828		-2.224	.028
	NLNPLR	.921	.159	.508	5.785	.000
	NLCAR	-.149	.399	-.033	-.373	.710
3	(Constant)	-6.826	1.283		-5.322	.000
	NLNPLR	.903	.144	.498	6.280	.000
	NLCAR	-.819	.387	-.180	-2.117	.037
	NLTA	.264	.055	.406	4.783	.000

By checking the variables (NPLR and CAR) in the presence of control variable NLTA, we found a slightest change in t-values and p-values of these variables. NLNPLR has a beta value .903 with t-value of 6.280 and p-value of 0.00. NLCAR has a beta value of -.819 with t-value of -2.117 and p-value of 0.37. NLTA has a beta

value of .264 with t-value of 4.783 and p-value of 0.000. The t-value of NPLR is greater than 2 and p-value is less than 0.05 which indicates a positive impact of NPLR on Return on Assets. However, t-value of CAR is less than 2 and p-value is greater than 0.05 which indicates a negative impact of CAR on Return on Assets.

Definitions of variables Return on assets (ROA)

The ratio of a company's net profit to its total resource (asset) is known as its ROA. It assesses the effectiveness of a bank's management in making profit from its scarce capital. The higher the return on investment, the more efficient will be the bank management, which is beneficial to the bank.

Return on Equity (ROE)

Besides ROA, another metric used to assess profitability is ROE. It is a net income-to-total-equity ratio. It is the rate of Return generated by the Equity of the shareholder.

Non-performing loan ratio (NPLR)

The NPLR is the major predictor of a bank's CR. It is the ratio of non-performing loans relative to the overall loans. It reflects the amount of a bank's loan and advances that have been non-performing, thus estimates the bank's credit default risk. The high value NPLR ratio sends a bad message for the bank management because it indicates a high possibility of none recovering the bank's main asset.

Capital adequacy ratio (CAR)

The amount of equity and other capital held by the bank against its volatile assets is referred to as CAR. This reserve exists to shield the depositor from unanticipated losses. Under the BASEL II accord, banks must have capital adequacy of at least 8% of their volatile assets.

Loan and advance to deposit ratio (LTRR)

The LTRR ratio tests a bank's ability to tolerate deposit withdrawals as well as its potential to satisfy loan demand by reducing cash reserves. Banks can reduce the risk of bankruptcy by increasing their liquidity. Since it ignores the combination of time and demand deposits, as well as other factors, this calculation gives more general detail on the deposit problem. Nonetheless, LTDR may be a valuable tool for evaluating a bank's liquidity.

Loan loss provision ratio (LLPR)

A loan loss reserve is a contra income account that helps banks to identify the estimated loss from a given loan portfolio in their profit and loss statements. Depositors are compensated by a capital adequacy reserve and a loan default provision reserve, which covers them from unanticipated losses. Banks will have LLP in their capital under Basel II. The general concept of LLP is that bank executives represent their views on the bank's asset quality. However, most experiments have discovered that administrators use this reserve for a variety of reasons, including income stabilisation and earnings control. As the level of Loan Loss Provision rises, the asset quality declines, and vice versa.

Discussion and Conclusion

The management of all types of risks is important for the same of growth of banking sector which is required for GDP and growth of country as well. The results suggested that risk management is the factor of performance. The capital adequacy ratio and non-performing loans are the factor of profitability which is used by commercial banks to measure the profitability. The study found that non-performing loan ratio (credit risk) has negative relationship with ROE. The negative relationship further confirms that higher the credit risk, lower would be the profitability among the commercial banks in Pakistan. Contrarily, the result shows that there is a positive and significant relationship of capital adequacy ratio with ROE. The positive relationship of capital adequacy ratio with ROE further confirms that higher the CAR, higher would be the profitability among the commercial banks in Pakistan. Similarly Hosna et al. (2009) delineate the positive relation of profitability with CAR and

negative with NPLR; that more the CAR more the profitability and more the NPLR less the profitability of banks. According to the results of the current analysis, CAR has a favourable significant effect on broad bank output (ROE) with a probability value of 0.00, which is less than 5%. Non-performing loans (NPL) are another risk control variable that has a major and detrimental effect on the ROE of big commercial banks, with likelihood values less than 5%.

The study also checked variables separately and in presence of control variable Size (NLTA). Thus it is found that NPLR has a positive relationship with ROA in both cases. Moreover, CAR has a positive relationship with ROE in both cases and a negative relationship with ROA. According to Haneef et al, (2012) regardless of much efforts made by the regulatory bodies (State Bank of Pakistan) and respective banks the amount of NPLs is growing consistently. NPL is also putting pressure for the revenue generation on the banking sector. Aduda, and Gitonga, (2011) has also argued with the study that the ROE tend to decline with the up surge in the ratio of nonperforming interest. Moreover the analysts have also asserted that the commercial banks which increases the ripple effect in their loan books suffers with the profitability issue. Therefore it is required to manage the loan books of commercial banks prudently in order to achieve higher level profitability which is possible with the help of CR management and proper portfolio monitoring. To stay stable in the industry, commercials must also insist on the efficiency of the loans, as well as their delivery and appraisal procedures. This research has strategic ramifications on both a national and international basis. At first it is also supported with respect to required capital with Basel Accord and it is found to be positive link in the profitability and the CR of banks. Second, the negative association between NPL and profit level suggests that non-performing loans are under management, which is a big concern in the banking sector on both a national and international level. And the problem is more significant in the banking history of Pakistan because of the wide role of politics in taking loans that later turned into non-performing loans. That is why banks are privatizing in order to gain further leverage. Third, the interest rate has a detrimental impact on the earnings of major commercial banks; the central bank should have interest rate ups and downs in order to help monitor the interest rate in terms of bank efficiency. This will serve as a warning to banking executives to better predict the structure's name. Liquidity risk must be kept in mind by banks in order to accept the conclusion that these risks have a negative impact on results. Finally, operational risk may necessitate the use of sound business models, procedures, and structures to reduce exposure operational risk under the supervision of the central bank, other world general banks, and the state bank of Pakistan in particular fields, as well as the implementation of applicable rules and regulations for the banking sector to reduce the incidence of these risks.

RECOMMENDATION

For proper persuasion of bank's regulations, there is need of sound credit analysis and provision of suitable credit loans circumstances. However, for avoidance of distorting the actual presentation of the bank's financial position on their balance sheet as well as compensation for the portfolio activities, these institutions should increase their focus on credit analysis. Moreover, they also need to report for the cyclic and seasonal phases of the economy along with loan credibility as well as appropriate management of portfolio. In addition, a robust and competent operational and credit risk management should be established by the commercial banks, which are governed by enforceable and unanimous policies. These polices may cover different aspects, such as proper check and balance of financing, best implementation of KYC (know your customer) and asset back policy for loans. Other important aspects are training and development and updated knowledge of employees regarding risk management practices. It eventually enables the bank and their overall administration to fulfill their responsibilities in an appropriate manner.

Conflict of Interests

The authors have not declared any conflict of interests.

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